

Interaction of Mercaptans with Phthalic Anhydride and Phthalyl Chloride.

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The condensation of phenols with anhydrides of dibasic acids has been extensively studied, the reaction giving rise to important dyestuffs belonging to the triphenylmethane series. No attempt appears as yet to have been made to condense mercaptans with these anhydrides in order to obtain the thio-analogues of these dyestuffs. The present investigation was undertaken with a view to bring about this reaction. Difficulty was encountered in the choice of a suitable condensing agent. Sulphuric acid, dry hydrochloric acid gas, anhydrous zinc chloride containing hydrogen chloride, and zinc chloride alone were tried and had to be rejected. The condensation between phthalic anhydride and aromatic mercaptans was, however, effected by employing phosphorus pentoxide.

The products, when isolated, lacked all the characteristic properties of phthaleins, *e.g.*, they were colourless, crystalline substances, insoluble in alkalis. The phthalein condensation evidently did not take place. The mercaptanic hydrogen atoms, owing to their enhanced reactivity, are eliminated (as water) in preference to the hydrogen atoms in the *ortho*- or *para*-position to the thiol group. In the reaction either the ketonic or the lactonic oxygen atom of the anhydride may be involved, giving rise to (I) or (II).

A choice between the thio-phthalide and the thioester constitution was arrived at from the fact that the compounds are not hydrolysed even by continued boiling with aqueous alkali. Had the products conformed to formula (I), the lactonic ring should have been opened by the treatment. Evidently thioesters of formula (II) are the exclusive products of the reaction. This view is supported by the fact

that various aliphatic mercaptans condense with phthalic anhydride in the same way.

The above results led the authors to investigate the action of the mercaptans on phthalyl chloride, which is known to exist in two tautomeric modifications,

In fact reactions in support of both these structures have long been known. Phthalyl chloride has been prepared in two isomeric forms by Ott (*Annalen*, 1912, 392, 245) and Csanyi (*Monatsh*, 1919, 40, 81). In the present instance phthalyl chloride was prepared by heating the anhydride for several hours with an equimolecular quantity of phosphorus pentachloride at 200° (*Annalen*, 1887, 238, 329). The chloride prepared in this way has been described by various investigators as reacting in either of the two tautomeric forms according to the conditions of the reaction. But the products of the condensation of the mercaptans with phthalyl chloride were found to be identical with those derived from the anhydride. With mercaptans at least phthalyl chloride behaves as if it had the symmetrical structure.

The constitution (I, R=Ph) assigned to the product of the reaction between phthalyl chloride and lead phenyl mercaptide by Troeger and Hornung (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1902, [ii], 66, 345) seems to be erroneous. The substance, prepared by them, crystallises in glistening leaflets, m. p. 84-85°. The present authors obtained two compounds by the condensation of phthalyl chloride with phenyl mercaptan. One is identical with Troeger and Hornung's whilst the other crystallises in colourless granules, m. p. 101°. But none of these could be hydrolysed by boiling with aqueous alkalis which indicates that neither has the lactonic structure adopted for one of them by Troeger and Hornung. These two compounds are isomeric and the difference between them is not yet clear.

Bis- β -naphthyl thiophthalide prepared by Troeger and Hornung (*loc. cit.*) is described as a compound crystallising from alcohol and melting at 153-54°. The authors obtained a product from phthalyl chloride and β -naphthyl mercaptan which is sparingly soluble in alcohol and on crystallising from amyl alcohol melts at 70° and froths on further rise of the temperature. The latter compound had all the properties of a thiophthalate.

These thio-esters can possibly be utilised in the synthesis of the hitherto unknown monothiophthalic and dithiophthalic acids. The preliminary part of this investigation is complete and will form the subject matter of a later communication.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Phenyl Mercaptan and Phthalic Anhydride.

Two molecules of phenyl mercaptan (4.4 g.) and one molecule of phthalic anhydride (6 g.) were heated together at 130-140° and to the liquid mixture phosphorus pentoxide (3 g.) was added and well stirred with a glass rod. After about three hours' heating the liquid was poured off leaving a black mass which was mostly phosphoric acid, tarry matter, and a small amount of the reaction products. The product which became semi-solid on cooling was dissolved in benzene, the solution was shaken with a dilute alkaline solution (2 to 3 times) and then well washed with water to remove alkali. It was then filtered, dehydrated with fused calcium chloride, again filtered and evaporated. The crystalline residue was dissolved in hot alcohol, boiled with animal charcoal, filtered and concentrated. The product, on recrystallisation, consisted of fine glistening leaflets of diphenyl dithiophthalate, m.p. 84-85°. (Found: S, 18.21.* $C_{20}H_{14}O_2S_2$ requires S, 18.28 per cent.)

The alcoholic mother-liquor was diluted with water until a turbidity was produced and then allowed to stand. A voluminous, granular, crystalline precipitate was obtained which was recrystallized from dilute alcohol, each time rejecting the first fraction of the crystals; m.p. 101°. (Found: C, 69.1; S, 18.97. $C_{20}H_{14}O_2S_2$ requires C, 68.57; S, 18.28 per cent.)

Phthalyl Chloride and Phenyl Mercaptan.

Two molecules (5.5 g.) of phenyl mercaptan were heated under reflux with 1 molecule of phthalyl chloride (5 g.) in dry benzene solution for 6-7 hours. Copious evolution of hydrochloric acid gas took place. The solution, after cooling, was treated like the benzene

* In this and in all the subsequent estimations of sulphur, the Carius' method was supplemented by fusion of the sodium salt of the sulphonic acid with potassium nitrate and sodium carbonate.

solution in the previous experiment and two compounds, one melting at 84-85° and the other melting at 101°, identical respectively with the compounds previously prepared, were obtained.

p-Bromothiophenol and Phthalic Anhydride.

A mixture of two molecules (4 g.) of the mercaptan and one molecule (1.5 g.) of the anhydride was heated to 130-140° and phosphorus pentoxide (2 g.) was added to the liquid mass and well stirred. The heating was continued for three hours and the temperature was finally raised to 160-70°. While hot, the liquid mass was poured off leaving behind a tarry material as before. The liquid, which solidified on cooling, was shaken with a small quantity of cold alcohol. The residue was dissolved in hot alcohol, boiled with animal charcoal and filtered hot. White granular crystals of dibromodiphenyl dithiophthalate were obtained, m.p. 186-188°. (Found: C, 47.16; H, 3.3. $C_{20}H_{12}O_2S_2Br_2$ requires C, 47.20; H, 2.4 per cent.)

The alcoholic extract, made in the cold, was evaporated to dryness and the residue was found to be mainly phthalic acid.

p-Bromothiophenol and Phthalyl Chloride.

One molecule of phthalyl chloride (2 g.) was heated to 130-40° and two molecules of the mercaptan (3.8 g.) were gradually added and the mass well stirred. Copious evolution of hydrochloric acid gas took place. The mass was heated for an hour and a half after all the mercaptan had been added, the temperature being finally raised to 160-70°. On cooling the mass solidified; it was shaken with cold alcohol and then crystallized from boiling alcohol. White granular crystals, m.p. 186-88°, identical with the previous compound, were obtained.

p-Iodophenyl Mercaptan and Phthalic Anhydride.

Two molecules of the mercaptan (4.7 g.), one molecule of the anhydride (1.5 g.) and phosphorus pentoxide (2 g.) were heated together as in the case of *p*-bromothiophenol. The crude reaction product was first washed with cold alcohol and then dissolved in hot benzene and precipitated with petroleum ether. The white, granular, light crystals of diiododiphenyldithiophthalate were well washed with petroleum ether; m.p. 181-82°. (Found: C, 39.9; H, 2.6. $C_{20}H_{12}O_2S_2I_2$ requires C, 39.8; H, 2.0 per cent.)

p-Iodothiophenol and Phthalyl Chloride.

One molecule of the acid chloride (2 g.) and two molecules (4.7 g.) of the mercaptan were taken, and the experiment conducted as in the case of the *p*-bromothiophenol. The crude product was purified as in the previous case. White granular crystals, m.p. 181-82°, identical with the previous compound were obtained.

Phe

p-Tolyl Mercaptan and Phthalic Anhydride.

The mercaptan (5 g.), the anhydride (3 g.) and phosphorus pentoxide (3 g.) were employed, and the experiment was conducted in a manner similar to that with *p*-bromothiophenol. The product, ditolyl dithiophthalate, was crystallized from hot alcohol with previous boiling with animal charcoal. White, needle-like, light crystals, m.p. 149°. (Found : C, 69.76 ; H, 5.3. C₁₆H₁₄O₂S₂ requires C, 69.84 ; H, 4.8 per cent.)

p-Tolyl Mercaptan and Phthalyl Chloride.

The mercaptan (5 g.) and the acid chloride (4 g.) were employed and the experiment conducted as in previous cases. The crude product on purification and crystallization from alcohol, gave white, needle-like crystals, m.p. 149°, identical with the previous compound.

β-Thionaphthol and Phthalic Anhydride.

The mercaptan (4.8 g.), the anhydride (2.2 g.) and phosphorus pentoxide (2 g.) were taken and the experiment conducted as in previous cases. The cooled oily crude product was first washed with cold alcohol and then dissolved in hot acetone and precipitated with petroleum ether, the product solidified after a time. It was then recrystallized either from amyl alcohol or a large amount of alcohol. Di-β-naphthyl thiophthalate forms white, fine, granular crystals, m.p. 70° with frothing on further heating. It is very soluble in carbon disulphide, chloroform, acetone, benzene, toluene, xylene or glacial acetic acid. (Found : C, 74.25 ; H, 3.99. C₁₆H₁₀O₂S₂ requires C, 74.70 ; H, 4.00 per cent.)

β -Thionaphthol and Phthalyl Chloride.

The mercaptan (3.2 g.) and the acid chloride (2 g.) were taken. The experiment was conducted and the crude product purified as before. White granular crystals, m.p. 70°, identical with the product already obtained.

Benzyl Mercaptan and Phthalic Anhydride.

The mercaptan (5 g.), acid anhydride (3 g.) and phosphorus pentoxide (3 g.) were taken and the experiment conducted as in previous cases. The dark brown crude oily product was dissolved in benzene and the solution was treated as before. Evaporation of benzene gave a deep brown thick oil. This was extracted with a small amount of ether leaving a small amount of brown solid residue. The ethereal solution was filtered and evaporated. This process was repeated 10-12 times until a transparent deep brown heavy oil (dibenzyl dithiophthalate) was obtained. (Found : S, 17.43. $C_{22}H_{18}O_2S_2$ requires S, 17.00 per cent.).

Benzyl Mercaptan and Phthalyl Chloride.

The mercaptan (2.5 g.) and the chloride (2 g.) were employed and the experiment conducted as usual. The compound was purified as above. The product was a deep brown oil, identical with the previous product.

Ethyl Mercaptan and Phthalyl Chloride.

The sodium salt of the mercaptan (3.3 g.) was suspended in dry benzene and the acid chloride (4 g.) was added to it ; the mixture was refluxed for about three hours. The solution was filtered to remove sodium chloride, shaken with a dilute alkaline solution repeatedly and then washed with water, filtered, dried and again filtered and evaporated. The mobile brown oil thus obtained was distilled in a vacuum but it decomposed. So it was purified by repeated extraction with small amount of ether as in the case of benzyl mercaptan compound. Diethyl dithiophthalate is soluble in alcohol, ether, acetone and benzene. (Found : S, 24.63. $C_{12}H_{14}O_2S_2$ requires S, 25.19 per cent.).

Propyl Mercaptan and Phthalyl Chloride.

The mercaptan (4.5 g.) and the acid chloride (6 g.) were heated in a sealed tube in the water-bath for about 6 hours. The crude

rown oil was next treated in the manner employed in the case of benzyl mercaptan. Vacuum distillation was also tried: the substance decomposed partly, a slightly brown mobile oil being obtained at 26 mm. pressure and 229-32°. The oil is soluble in alcohol, ether or benzene. (Found : S, 23.44. $C_{14}H_{18}O_2S$, requires S, 22.69 per cent.).

Butyl Mercaptan and Phthalyl Chloride.

The mercaptan (3.6 g.) and the acid chloride (4 g.) were heated together under reflux for about 3 hours. The deep brown oil was repeatedly shaken with dilute alkali. It was then extracted with ether and the solution well washed with water, filtered, dried, again filtered and evaporated : a light brown oil was obtained which was kept in vacuum for several days. Fine white needle-shaped crystals deposited which were separated. The oil, when crystals no longer separated, was dissolved in a small amount of ether. The solution was filtered and evaporated, and on analysis was found to be the disulphide of the mercaptan. The crystals were pressed on porous plate and then repeatedly crystallized from petroleum ether. White needle-shaped crystals (dibutyl dithiophthalate), m.p. 56-57°. (Found : S, 21.34. $C_{16}H_{22}O_2S_2$, requires S, 20.64 per cent.).

Ethylene Mercaptan and Phthalyl Chloride.

The mercaptan (1.9 g.) and the acid chloride (4 g.) were heated together at 110-20° for an hour and a half. The cooled solid mass was washed with cold alcohol and crystallized from hot alcohol. White crystals of diethylenesulphide dithiophthalate, m.p. 169°, were obtained. (Found : C, 51.2; H, 3.97. $C_{12}H_{14}O_2S_2$, requires C, 50.7; H, 4.2 per cent.).

This experiment was repeated with twice the amount of mercaptan, when the same product was obtained in larger yield.

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